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Deliverable D1.1 - Mapping of existing citizen engagement initiatives

WP1 – Mapping citizens engagement practices to improve Climate Resilience

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1. Executive summary

This report (Deliverable 1.1 (D1.1)) presents an overview of the tasks conducted to map existing databases of citizen engagement initiatives, as well as existing initiatives related to climate change adaptation. The task started with a literature review to find the scope of what means ‘citizen engagement’ and understand in which forms it can take place under deliberative democracy exercises. The aim was to identify initiatives which opted for empowering forms of engagement using discursive practices, rather than for instance, relying on one-way communication with citizens. Once the concept boundaries were set, the mapping exercise initially gathered information about webpages, platforms, and projects which had constructed databases of citizen engagement. These databases were analysed to identify key themes tracked and the underpinning research, supporting the process of building in a second stage a registration tool to map additional citizen engagement initiatives specifically targeting climate change adaptation.

In total, we describe 13 databases identified and 61 citizen engagement initiatives in their key characteristics. The main results show how:

- Citizen engagement is present across governance levels, from the local to the national.
- Citizen engagement for climate change adaptation specifically is less spread relative to processes focusing on other issues of concern, such as climate change mitigation.
- Certain types of citizen engagement initiatives are widely used, such as citizen assemblies and they display a homogeneous format.
- Few initiatives incorporate an evaluation process, which could yield important information about the learning processes and impacts of such deliberative forms of democracy.

The outcomes of this research are relevant because they are the backbone of building knowledge on citizen engagement practices, research conducted under task 1.2 in Work Package 1.

2. Background of WP1

WP1’s main goal is to **identify existing practices and resources related to citizen engagement**.

This includes mapping: 1) existing citizen engagement initiatives and databases as presented here (T1.1); and 2) capacity building resources focusing on both citizen engagement and fighting climate misinformation. This latter activity (2) was submitted in M12 as ‘D1.3 Report on capacity building resources on climate change adaptation and disinformation campaigns’ following the efforts carried out under task (T) 1.3 ([link](#)). The third pillar is an 3) analysis of citizen engagement practices. Accordingly, three tasks contribute to the fulfilment of the overall objectives (the institution in brackets is the lead partner):

- **Task 1.1** Review and update existing mapping of citizen engagement initiatives related to climate adaptation in Europe [BSC].
- **Task 1.2** Analyse methodologies and practices employed to engage citizens [BSC].

- **Task 1.3** Compile and analyse capacity building resources for climate change adaptation and fighting disinformation campaigns [IBE].

This deliverable describes the objectives of the first task (1) in Work Package (WP) 1 of the AGORA project: '**T1.1 Review and update existing mapping of citizen engagement initiatives related to climate adaptation in Europe**'. The following sections contextualise this main objective and subsequently describe the activities conducted during M1-M18 to fulfil the task.

Box 1 provides a description of the activities which were expected under T1.1, which this deliverable will then detail how they were put in practice.

Box 1 Task 1.1 description and expected activities, as detailed in the Grant Agreement

Review and update existing mapping of citizen engagement initiatives related to climate adaptation in Europe (M1-M18)

This task will focus on reviewing existing mapping exercises (webpages, platforms, reports, documents, maps etc.) that identify projects, initiatives and activities engaging citizens on topics related to climate change adaptation (e.g., WeObserve, EU-Citizen.Science, weADAPT, PANORAMA) as well as in marine and freshwater domains in relation to climate, (e.g., FreshWater Watch). This will be achieved through desk research, literature review and interviews with key informants of existing initiatives to gain further insights, applying the snowball sampling technique. This task will be the basis for Task 1.2., which is the backbone for providing a toolbox of mechanisms of citizen and stakeholder engagement as expected inputs to be represented in the Digital Agora (Task 3.3).

As per the task description, the exercise consisted of reviewing and updating existing mappings of citizen engagement initiatives related to climate adaptation in Europe.

2.1. Summary of (sub)objectives, efforts and accomplishments.

Carrying out the activities to fulfil T1.1 supported several other objectives of the AGORA project. This is especially the case for the desk research activities undertaken to update the existing mapping of initiatives, which involved identifying and contacting organisations, databases and projects related to citizen engagement (for more details, see section 3). Because of the nature of this activity, it supported the following AGORA objectives:

- **[O5]** Alliances of high impact, in order to increase the likelihood of long-term sustainability and social acceptability of citizen-led actions in the context of the Mission adaptation.
- **[Communication and Dissemination]** AGORA communication and dissemination will capitalize on networking activities with other projects.
- **[Links to other tasks]** T1.1 is the basis for T1.2, which is itself the backbone for “providing a toolbox of mechanisms of citizen and stakeholder engagement as expected inputs to be represented in the Digital Agora (T3.3)”.

We return back to how T1.1 supported these objectives in the concluding section of this deliverable.

3. Detail of work done

3.1. Introduction

Mapping examples of citizen engagement initiatives and existing databases requires a definition of how we understand ‘citizen engagement initiative’ in the context of the AGORA project. To complete the first part of this task, we conducted an unstructured literature review to define the concept boundaries by identifying key seminal works related to ‘citizen engagement’ and ‘citizen participation’, such as Arnstein’s Ladder of Participation or Delli Carpini and colleagues (see next).

The term ‘citizen engagement’ has been adopted by the EU Missions and the concept is equally common in academic and grey literatures (Delli Carpini et al., 2004; Adler et al., 2005; Ekman et al., 2012). Nonetheless, there are other terms used that may imply the same, such as ‘public participation’, ‘direct democracy’ or ‘democratic innovations’. The scope of these similar terms give rise to fuzzy boundaries because there is no universally agreed definition of citizen engagement. The concept is moreover put in practice differently across democratic governance systems, and different actors within them create a wide range of interpretations when citizen engagement is implemented. This diversity of interpretations thus generates the need for a working definition on which to base the mapping.

3.2. Defining concept boundaries: literature and scoping review of existing initiatives

For the purposes of the AGORA project, we are interested specifically in how citizens can be empowered to contribute to decisions related to climate change adaptation. We do not seek to include initiatives in which citizens participate but are not empowered (e.g., where they are informed about adaptation action in a one-directional manner). Using this more active interpretation of engagement pushes us to interpret citizen engagement under the broader umbrella of deliberative democracy. Here also interpretations vary, but we adopt Delli Carpini et al.’s (2004) definition of deliberative democracy as something that “focuses on the communicative processes of opinion and will formation that precede voting [and any other form of political participation]”. Within the concept of deliberative democracy, there exists the act of *public deliberation*. As such, public deliberation is the ‘gathering place’ where deliberative democracy occurs, and we again follow Delli Carpini et al. (2004) to adopt the definition below of public deliberation from Gastil (2000: p. 22):

“Public deliberation is discussion that involves judicious argument, critical listening, and earnest decision making. Following the writings of John Dewey, full deliberation includes a careful examination of a problem or issue, the identification of possible solutions, the establishment or reaffirmation of evaluative criteria, and the use of these criteria in identifying an optimal solution. Within a specific policy debate or in the context of an election, deliberation sometimes starts with a given set of solutions, but it always involves problem analysis, criteria specification, and evaluation.”

From this definition, we can already see important activities that take place during Citizen Engagement Initiatives (CEIs), such as deliberation around a specific problem – in our case action or interventions related to climate change adaptation processes – and the identification of possible solutions in often consensus-based deliberation. These are aspects that are important for the operationalisation that we propose in subsection 3.2.1. Seen under this light, CEIs thus imply *discursive* participation, which is characterized as being talk-centric compared to vote-centric activities like political participation. The mainstream emergence of discursive participation occurred as part of the deliberative turn that took place in the early 2000s (Jacobs et al., 2009), and has also recently been reinforced in the context of the climate crisis (Willis et al., 2022). A key aspect that we embrace here is that the process of discursive participation and deliberation are as important as the outcomes (the proposed solutions, for example), as illustrated in the following quote from Chambers (2003, p. 309):

*“Generally speaking, we can say that **deliberation is debate and discussion aimed at producing reasonable, well-informed opinions in which participants are willing to revise preferences in light of discussion, new information, and claims made by fellow participants.** Although consensus need not be the ultimate aim of deliberation, and participants are expected to pursue their interests, an overarching interest in the legitimacy of outcomes (understood as justification to all affected) ideally characterizes deliberation.”*

The quote also alludes to five key conditions for assessing public deliberation: universalism, inclusivity, rationality, agreement, and political efficacy (Jacobs et al., 2009, pp. 9 - 13), which will underpin the analysis of citizen engagement methodologies and practices to be undertaken in T1.2. Figure 1 summarises our pathway to framing and defining CEIs.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the theoretical basis for citizen engagement initiatives

3.2.1. What counts as engagement?

From the theoretical perspectives in the literature, we now move to outline a practical working definition of ‘citizen engagement’ to use for our mapping and evaluation of initiatives. This definition is relevant because additionally, it touches upon types of participation, and it helps limit the scope for what citizen engagement encompasses or not.

We adopt the following four characteristics of public deliberation that are important, relevant, and which frame citizen engagement as a category within ‘discursive participation’.

To be included in our mapping, a citizen engagement initiative:

Must:

- Include **discourse with other citizens**: actions of talking, discussing, debating, and/or deliberating, i.e., we expressly consider “talking” as a form of participation¹.
- Focus on a local, national, or international issue of public concern; for the AGORA project this specifically refers to **climate change adaptation** action.

Can:

- Be linked to civic and political processes.
- Occur through a **variety of media** (not only face-to-face exchanges).

As well as helping identify in-scope examples, the process of defining a CEI also influenced the CEI characteristics we tracked in the mapping exercise (see below).

3.2.2. Range of existing practices

Employing the CEI definition above in preliminary database searches allowed us to list an array of activities that may be considered as CEI; these include:

- Deliberative mini-publics
- Panels
- Conversation cafés
- Roundtables
- Councils
- Forums/forum theatres
- Dialogues

Within these broad groupings, it was quickly apparent that certain approaches follow a specific set of practices building up to a methodology, as is the case for some forms of deliberative mini-publics.

Table 1 compares different types of deliberative mini-publics and their main characteristics. Citizen ('climate') assemblies were among the most easily identifiable examples of CEIs for climate-related policy processes, as many countries have organised such initiatives at national level to yield recommendations from a randomly selected group of citizens. From the types identified in the table, and as it will be shown in section 4 ('Analysing the data'), citizen juries are also used in some occasions.

Table 1. Types of deliberative mini-publics and their main characteristics (Elstub, 2014)

	<i>Citizens' juries</i>	<i>Planning Cells</i>	<i>Consensus conferences</i>	<i>Deliberative polls</i>	<i>Citizens' assemblies</i>
Developed by (first instance)	Crosby (USA, 1971)	Dienel (Germany, 1970s)	Danish Board of Technology (1987)	James Fishkin (USA, 1994)	Gordon Gibson (Canada, 2002)
No. of citizens	12-26	100-500	10-25	100-500	100-160
No. of meetings	2-5 days	4-5 days	7-8 days	2-3 days	20-30 days
Selection method	Random selection	Random selection	Random + self-selection	Random selection	Random + self-selection
Activities	Information + deliberation	Information + deliberation	Information + deliberation	Information + deliberation	Information +consultation +deliberation
Result	Collective position report	Survey opinions + Collective position report	Collective position report	Survey opinions	Detailed recommendation
Destination of proposal	Sponsor and mass media	Sponsor and mass media	Parliament and mass media	Sponsor and mass media	Parliament, government and public referendum

However, deliberative mini-publics are often resource intensive, so we were also keen to include other types of initiatives that exist and that take place across governance levels. These other types tend to have less strict methodological structures and show a wider range of forms in which they are implemented. For instance, they may or may not involve purposive selection of citizens, and in some cases there is no minimum number of participants required, both of which are usually the case for citizen assemblies. The intention of our broad-focussed mapping exercise for existing initiatives was to take into account this diversity in existing initiatives.

Finally, beyond our definition of CEIs and relevant practices, our mapping is limited to recent initiatives, i.e., those conducted from 2018 onwards in Europe. There are several reasons for this choice: firstly, the aim is to account for the impacts of COVID-19, having some observations prior to the pandemic, some during, and after, when engagement initiatives could return to face-to-face meetings. This yielded approximately 2 years of each. Secondly, in the analysis of databases (see section 3.2.4.) it was noticed how the bulk of observations ranged many up until 2018, and the task description specifically mentioned providing an update of existing mappings and initiatives.

3.2.3. Characteristics to include

To understand the mapped landscape of CEIs, it was necessary to not only list the relevant CEIs, but also document some of their characteristics. With a view to help the AGORA community find

relevant examples of CEIs for their own work, we collected simple headline data on where and when the CEIs were carried out, and what adaptation aspects they focused on.

Beyond this, given the aim of supporting the analysis of what is effective engagement in T1.2, we also sought to begin to interrogate how the CEIs were carried out. This deeper analysis is not the focus of this task, but for coherence between the tasks we also included an overview of high-level features that contributes to our ongoing assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of CEIs. For example, the literature research conducted to support the definition of CEIs suggested it was important to detail the actors that started the CEI, differentiating between citizen participatory initiatives (which are usually started by local communities) and citizen engagement initiatives (which are usually started by governments). Beyond starting the initiative, we also found that the roles that governments and public offices play during the CEI also should be identified to help assess aspects such as legitimacy. Thus, the mapping includes aspects such as who decides on the ‘issues of public concern’, engagement methods or evaluation criteria, and how different groups contribute to different parts of the process and outputs, because these can all impact the degree to which a CEI achieves key conditions (e.g., universalism, inclusivity, rationality, agreement, and political efficacy). Full details of the mapped characteristics are provided in section 3.2.5.

3.2.4. Mapping of existing CEI databases

Gathering data to identify databases involved a preliminary desk research phase to scan existing mapping initiatives, followed by a more intense phase in which several methods were deployed to supplement relevant CEIs found in existing databases with non-listed CEIs. In more detail, the two activities consisted of:

- **Desk research:** identifying existing databases, webpages, EU-funded projects, academic and grey literature, including those listed in the AGORA proposal and suggestions from partners.
- **Mixed-methods:** snow-ball sampling and participant observation during related events such as conferences or workshops, or via outreach to umbrella organizations that were willing to distribute the registration tool (see section 3.2.6).

We found numerous databases that collect information about CEIs and which are variously maintained by academic, practitioner and government (EU) actors. Although the databases are often large (ranging from dozens to, in some cases, thousands of entries), filtering the initiatives according to our criteria (deliberative engagement in climate change adaptation activities in Europe since 2018) severely reduces the number of potential CEIs, suggesting that none are in any way exhaustive. Nonetheless, even in cases where the databases added few applicable CEIs, they often provided resources and potential contacts for snow-ball mapping (this task) and expert survey/interviews (T1.2).

The table below presents a summary of the aims and coverage of 13 databases which appeared to include relevant entries. We include high-level details relevant to our aim of creating a source of

specific and relevant information for practitioners and researchers interested in recent climate adaptation CEIs in Europe, i.e., the coverage and scope of, the number of initiatives (total and AGORA-relevant), and the ease of searching within the database for specific types of CEI. In many cases, a lack of immediately available details make it unclear if a database entry is relevant to AGORA.

Table 2. Summary characteristics of databases including climate adaptation and citizen engagement case studies

Name	Maintained by	Key theme	Types of initiatives	Dates	Spatial coverage	Number of cases (of which relevant)	CEI Mapping Functionality
AdapteCCa.es	Spanish Government	Experiences, initiatives and projects on climate change adaptation	All	Unclear – present	Spain	42 (7)	Basic
Bürgerrat	Mehr Demokratie	Public participation and democratic innovations	Various (e.g., assemblies, juries, councils, fora)	Unclear – present	Germany, EU, Global	~600 (unclear)	Basic
Cities profile	EUROCITIES	CEIs in cities	Unclear (no avail. summaries)	Unclear - present	Europe	16 (unclear)	Basic
Citizen Engagement EU	Fraunhofer Institute	CE methods, resources, case studies	All	2016 – 2019	Global	90 (0)	Advanced
Citizen Engagement Navigator	EC Community of Practice of the Competence Centre on Participatory and Deliberative Democracy	EU Projects with CEI themes	All	2008 – 2023	Europe	52 (5)	Intermediate
Climate Adapt Case Studies	European Commission	Climate Adaptation Knowledge Platform	All	2016 - present	Europe	129 (20)	Intermediate
Ecsite	Ecsite (European network of science centres and museums)	Engaging citizens in science, Mutual Learning,	EU research projects featuring CE in science	2006 – present	Europe	49 (1)	Basic
KNOCA	Knowledge Network on Climate Assemblies	Climate Assemblies	Climate Assemblies	2018 – present	Europe	~50 (all)	Basic
Mini-Publics Map	TU Berlin	Understanding the growth and spread of mini-publics	Deliberative mini-publics	1970-2019	Global	2170 (4)	Basic
OECD Deliberative Democracy Database	OECD	Citizen Participation / Deliberative Democracy	All	1979 – 2023	Global	733 (4)	Advanced
Participatory Methods (examples and case studies)	Institute of Development Studies (IDS)	Citizen Participation / Deliberative Democracy Tools	All	1993 – present	Global	22 (0)	Basic
Participedia	International expert volunteer network	Public participation and democratic innovations	All	2013 – present	Global	2225 (~20)	Advanced
Politicize.eu	Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB)	Formal, large (national/regional) European initiatives	Deliberative mini publics	2000 – present	Europe	159 (9)	Intermediate

3.2.5. Finding the niche: the need for the AGORA CEI dataset

The review of databases that included potentially relevant CEIs demonstrates the need for a dataset that compiles recent experiences of deliberative collaboration focused on climate change adaptation. In particular, we found that even in very large databases there were few examples that met our criteria. For example, there were lots of CEIs that occurred before 2018 and many collaborative adaptation efforts that focussed on stakeholder - rather than citizen - engagement. Reflecting the bias mentioned in the recent review of engagement initiatives by Revez et al. (2022), many of the climate-related initiatives focused on mitigation activities related to energy systems and sustainable consumption (e.g., Bürgerrat). Equally, there were many other examples of community projects that touch upon climate change adaptation issues but did not seem to have them as their core concern and as such were considered out of scope for AGORA, (e.g., transition towns, transiscope). This relates to a broader challenge we encountered in finding adaptation-focussed actions that may not have been labelled as adaptation.

With these findings in mind, the next steps consisted of designing a data-collection tool that would allow us to register CEIs and populate the AGORA database. We highlight that the aim of this tool was to complement and learn from the experiences generated by the magnificent work done across the databases mentioned above.

3.2.6. Designing our own data collection tool (for initiatives)

Following our review of the literature and existing databases, we identified fields that are important to map in as part of T1.1 to create a searchable database of recent adaptation-relevant CEIs in Europe. These fields are categorised under three topics and described below. These categories were agreed in advance with the AGORA Consortium to ensure that, as well as informing T1.2, the database contained the additional fields required to gather data that supports efforts in other work packages. The structure was also shared with colleagues working on the Digital AGORA to ensure it can feed into the platform as it is developed.

Project identity

The initial fields identify the CEI, including the name, if it is linked to a project, its type, location, and start and end date. This section also includes details of relevant contacts (people or projects) to display with the initiative when it is uploaded to the Digital AGORA. The final part of this section includes a semi-structured description of the initiative and the possibility to upload a picture to accompany the entry.

Objectives

The second set of input fields refer to the CEIs' objectives and broader goals, the climate hazard(s) it sought and the climate change adaptation subsector (drawn from the [climateADAPT platform](#)).

Key characteristics

The next fields map the key characteristics of initiatives:

- Scale of the project, i.e., the administrative level of the process and outputs
- Type of initiative
- Number of separate meetings
- Where the meetings took place
- Number of citizens involved
- How citizens were selected
- Engagement methods used

Stakeholder involvement and roles

CEIs potentially involve a wide range of stakeholders alongside citizens, from policymakers to subject experts, consultancies and NGOs. This field therefore identifies which stakeholders were involved during the initiative and their role(s). The range of roles that stakeholders can play included are:

- Participant: being part of the deliberation process
- Organiser: proposing or commissioning the initiative
- Implementer: conducting the deliberation process (“facilitators”)
- Funder: funds from which the process is being financed
- Expert: people invited to give a talk about a specific climate-related topic
- Advisor: the person or entity acts as observant to ensure certain criteria are respected
- Other: possible other roles (brokerage, non-financial sponsor, etc.)

To account for individuals potentially playing several roles, and for each category potentially including various individuals with different contributions, this field has multiple choice options and an open field to introduce such information.

Engagement output

The fields under this theme detail the final output of the engagement process, which includes the format and impact of any decisions. As our preliminary literature review suggested the impacts of CEIs are less studied, we also explicitly assess whether there is any evaluation process linked to the initiative. Evaluating citizen engagement initiatives is essential for assessing their effectiveness and ensuring accountability. Moreover, it can provide valuable feedback for continuous learning and improvement, help build a knowledge base for evidence-based practice, and enhance participation and ownership (Few et al., 2007; Reed et al., 2009).

Launching the tool

Finally, we iteratively tested and developed several prototypes before deploying the version currently in use. This gives us relative confidence that the tool contains all the explained fields, is

straightforward to use, allows for consistency in gathering the data for each CEI, and allows us to filter and download the collated data in standard formats.

The tool can be accessed here: <https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/CEImap>

Figure 2. Screenshot of the registration tool (initial fields)

Agora
just and inclusive
climate adaptation

Citizen engagement initiatives - registration tool

Mapping citizen engagement initiatives in Europe on climate change adaptation

Background/Context
We are delighted to invite you to register a **Citizen Engagement Initiative (CEI)** in the forthcoming Digital AGORA online database. This mapping exercise is part of a European Commission-funded research project called AGORA that seeks to actively involve communities and regions in climate actions providing a comprehensive package of digital tools and co-developed frameworks (<https://adaptationagora.eu/>). The Digital AGORA will include a searchable database of adaptation-focused CEIs around Europe, which we hope will facilitate knowledge sharing and will form the basis for our efforts to draw together the best practices on how to engage citizens in climate change adaptation themes.

Important Information
There is a very wide range of interpretations of Citizen Engagement Initiatives (CEIs), which are also sometimes known as Public Participation activities. We focus specifically on those participatory processes with citizens that are linked to matters of public concern on climate change adaptation and include any form of **discursive interaction**, such as talking, discussing, debating and deliberating.

How to include your CEI
This tool is designed to be manageable for data analysis and for searching for initiatives. Providing as much detail as possible will help us understand the universe of CEIs and help others to find your CEI. However, there may be sections of the tool that do not apply to your CEI. Please leave any non-applicable questions blank, and add any other information you think is relevant in the open field (the last question). On average, it takes around **10 minutes to add one CEI**. We kindly ask that you add separate CEIs individually.

Data protection
If you would like any of your contact details to be published on the Digital Agora platform along with the information about your Citizen Engagement Initiative, please provide them below. This data will be stored and processed by the partners of the Agora project and will not be used for further distribution or any other purpose than the one mentioned above.

If you have any questions, comments or concerns about the mapping tool, the AGORA project or our wider work on citizen engagement, please contact: Eulàlia Baulenas or Sam Pickard (Barcelona Supercomputing Center) at eulalia.baulenas@bsc.es / samuel.pickard@bsc.es

1. Please provide some general details about the project

Project name

Location

Country

Start (Month/Year)

End (Month/Year or "Ongoing")

Website (project's own or other information source)

3.2.7. Data collection efforts I: contacting umbrella organisations and EU-funded projects

Once the CEI registration tool was ready, it was distributed to a set of European organisations identified during the desk research activities that promoted citizen engagement for issues of public interest in their mission statements.

Table 3. Organisations consulted during data collection efforts

N	Name of organisations
1	MissionAdapt
2	European Citizen Action Service (ECAS)
3	European Movement International (EMI)
4	Citizens for Europe (web)
5	European Youth Forum (web)
6	European Civic Forum (web)
7	Eurocities (web)
8	European Science Engagement Association (EUSEA)
9	European network for COmmunity-Led Initiatives on climate change and sustainability (ECOLISE)
10	European Citizen Science Platform (ECS)
11	Swedish National Knowledge Centre for Climate Change Adaptation
12	Klimatiksdragen (https://klimatriksdagen.se/)
13	Italian Climate Network (https://www.italiaclima.org/)
14	Alleanza Italiana per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile (ASviS)
15	Legambiente
16	Bürgerbüro

The organisations were contacted either directly by the authors or via internal contacts from the AGORA consortium during the months of January to March 2024. The partners that supported these efforts were ICLEI, ECSA, CIMA, IIASA and University of Geneva.

We received 10 positive responses, 1 negative, and 5 non-responses. For those who responded positively, the next step of the exchange included a brief call to present the AGORA project, present the activities that could be of interest to the umbrella organisation and finally, describe WP1 and request if the CEI registration tool could be distributed across their network.

We also contacted several projects with activities pertinent to WP1 themes (e.g., either carried out citizen engagement or included a network that may be interested in knowing about the registration tool and the AGORA project). As such, this activity supported efforts to promote project clustering, one of the wider AGORA objectives that this WP has contributed to. Five of the following ten projects agreed to add their own initiatives to the AGORA tool.

Transform project	TransformAr
POCITYF	Maptionnaire
Civitas Elan	WeObserve
ARSINOE	ACCTING
IMPETUS	Dialog Klimanpassung

Finally, several consortium partners disseminated the CEI registration tool through their networks via social media channels, newsletters, and when participating in conferences and networking events. This was the case for the ECSA and ICLEI newsletters, and for University of Geneva in the Climate Europe Festival in Venice, March 2024. The AGORA newsletter and social media channels also distributed the tool, as well as the EC Community of Practice's Competence Centre for Participatory and Deliberative Democracy.

3.2.7. Data collection efforts II: adding initiatives to our database

To complement asking CEIs to self-register, we also undertook desk research to allow us to add identified initiatives to the tool ourselves. This strategy was less favoured than asking those with knowledge of CEIs to self-register them for several reasons: 1) there is often only partial information online about initiatives; in many cases, 2) information that is available is only available for the larger initiatives (e.g., those with enough funds to have a website and document what happened); and 3) contacting others provides an opportunity to disseminate AGORA activities, which is missed if we add them ourselves. Nonetheless, this strategy allowed us to be more exhaustive in the mapping of initiatives included in the database.

These data collection efforts focussed on the pilot regions of the AGORA project: Germany, Italy, Spain and Sweden. Although for Sweden the efforts were less successful, this explains why these countries have an over-representation of mapped initiatives relative to other countries (see section 4.2).

4. Analysing the data

Although the tool remains open and we continue to add initiatives as we find them, to conduct the analysis that follows, it was necessary to define an end point for the data collection presented here. Thus, at the time of finalising this deliverable (May 2024) we had mapped 61 initiatives. Despite the distribution efforts, only 24 were added by external contacts; we added the remaining 37. This has consequences in that it might bias our analysis towards those initiatives with enough budget to be present online and with enough information available, such as it is the case for citizen assemblies. Our plans for overcoming this potential bias are described in subsection 5.1: Foundations for 1.2.

4.1. Data cleaning and verification

The first step to clean the data was to homogenise the observations. For instance, ensuring the start and end of the project were in a coherent format rather than the mixture of forms we permitted in the tool.

The collected data was then verified against the resources added externally. As a result, three initiatives were removed from the dataset to be analysed because they did not fit the scope, as they did not have any engagement with citizens but with local initiatives. As the data serves two purposes, conducting this analysis and being displayed in the Digital AGORA, two datasets were

created with these non-analysed entries preserved for the dataset destined for the Digital Agora (which has a broader scope that includes non-CEI projects).

4.2. Analysis of initiatives

Geographical representation and scale

Table 4 displays the countries with more than one reported citizen engagement initiative. Other countries represented in the sample with one initiative were Austria, Cyprus, Denmark, France, Greece, Ireland, Poland, Serbia, Switzerland and Turkey. The majority of the entries reflect separate initiatives, but two research projects had parallel processes being carried out in several locations (Italy, Cyprus, Portugal and Serbia; and Italy and Spain).

The majority of initiatives were at the municipal level (31 involved one municipality, 4 involved several), followed by the subnational/state level, and the national level. There was also one cross-national process accounting for 4 initiatives.

Figure 3. Map of registered initiatives	Table 4. Geographical count of CEIs (>1)																			
	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Country</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Italy</td> <td>14</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Germany</td> <td>13</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Spain</td> <td>8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>UK</td> <td>6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Belgium</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Sweden</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Portugal</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td>51</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Country	Count	Italy	14	Germany	13	Spain	8	UK	6	Belgium	5	Sweden	3	Portugal	2	Total	51	
Country	Count																			
Italy	14																			
Germany	13																			
Spain	8																			
UK	6																			
Belgium	5																			
Sweden	3																			
Portugal	2																			
Total	51																			

Table 5. Institutional scale of the initiatives

Institutional scale	Count
Local (town, city)	31
Supralocal (several municipalities)	4
Subregional (province)	3
Subnational (e.g., Catalonia, Bavaria)	10
National	6
Supranational	3
Cross-border	4
Total	61

The large presence of Germany case studies is also due to the reliance on the Bürgerrat database for German-based CEIs (section 3.2.4). However, even here only 13 of the 96 initiatives listed on the Bürgerrat website were found to be adaptation relevant (focusing on urban planning or future visions of locals and citizens’ quality of life). By comparison, 15 focussed on climate mitigation. Even within the 13 available, those focusing on citizens quality of life are likely over-represented because they relate to a prototype initiative conducted by a single consultancy company in several localities. Overall, Germany serves here as a paradigmatic case for a trend being observed during the assessment of databases. Whilst we can observe that citizen engagement seems to be widely spread across governance levels in a variety of issues, it is only recently and in a minority of cases that climate change adaptation is targeted. We will return to this in section 5 (‘Next steps’).

Climate change adaptation sector and impacts

The registered initiatives centred around climate change adaptation in general terms (14), followed by urban planning (10), energy (9) and natural resources (5 on water management; 5 on agriculture; 2 on biodiversity; 1 on the environment in general). Consumption, land use planning, tourism and transport were represented in 1 process.

Several initiatives, especially those using a Citizen Assembly-type of methodology, covered several topics during the engagement process:

- Energy; financial; transport; business and industry.
- Consumption; food systems; waste.

Some of the registered initiatives also considered climate change impacts and trends – which is a multiple-choice item in the registration tool. The most commonly addressed impacts were temperature related - extreme heat events (20) and warmer climate over time (10), followed by those related to water - floods (19 of which 12 related to surface water, 7 to river floods), droughts (12), heavy rainfall (12), and drier climate over time (5).

Type of initiative

Figure 4 shows the types of initiatives. The most common type across the mapped initiatives followed a citizen assembly approach (23). This large representation is likely a result of the potential bias suggested earlier where initiatives with larger budgets were more easily identified online. Dialogues (7), Citizens’ panels (6), public budgeting (5) and roundtables (5) were also relatively common.

Figure 4. Types of initiatives represented in the mapping

Goals

Individual CEIs often have several goals. Thus, the use of a multiple-choice field in the registration tool resulted in the following goals:

- Better decision-making/policy outcomes (28)
- Public education and/or capacity building (26)
- Public inclusion and/or empowerment (24)
- Strengthen democracy (22)
- Social innovation and problem-solving (13)
- Increased trust in government/legitimacy (10)
- Enhanced transparency and accountability (7)
- Improved service delivery (5)
- Increased social cohesion (4)

Better decision-making and/or policy outcomes was the most often chosen goal, followed by public education and/or capacity building, with public inclusion and/or empowerment close after. Compatible with these overarching goals, 22 initiatives aimed to strengthen democracy, which is in the baseline of the arguments in favour of deliberative democracy, as mentioned in section 3. Less often mentioned but also present were the other goals asked for – and it is important to note that no goal listed in the registration tool was left blank. Other goals were also suggested, including to renew modes of governance, to achieve better mental and physical well-being or behavioural change, as well as environmental awareness.

Figure 5 disaggregates the headline figures by initiative type and level of government, to observe whether patterns emerged in the choice of a certain type or the level. Although we do not have

enough data to be conclusive, a cursory analysis suggests the most that panels and meetings did not target the most common goal of better decision-making/policy outcomes; nor did public budgeting or forums focus on strengthening of democracy.

Figure 5. Goals across CEI types and governance levels

Timespan, number of meetings and location

The initiatives vary greatly in their timespan as well as in the number of meetings. This is especially the case across types of initiatives, with more similarities observed within types. Citizen assemblies, for instance, generally have 1-2 introductory meetings, 2-3 topic discussion meetings (in which experts explain aspects related to the issue in focus), 1-2 deliberative meetings, and 1 final meeting to present the set of recommendations to the governmental body. These thus also tended to represent longer processes, although the longest projects stem from initiatives within the LIFE or Erasmus+ EU-funded projects.

Figure 6. Number of months

Figure 7. Number of meetings

The largest group of initiatives were conducted face-to-face (28), generally in a public facility such as the city council or cultural centres. Some were hybrid (9) which in some cases was due to COVID-19, and a minority (5) were conducted online only. For regional and national initiatives, some respondents reported that the meeting location changed during the series of initiatives.

In terms of the selection of citizens, and largely driven by data from citizen assemblies, the most common option was random selection (18), whilst 15 used open invites and 13 chose targeted sampling. Self-selection - where the implementers select participants from a group of volunteers - was used by 3 CEIs while ad hoc selection was used by 1.

Figure 8. Selection method of initiatives (n)

Role(s) of actors

Figure 8 shows the role(s) of different actors during the initiatives. Aside from a few cases where they acted as implementers or advisors, citizens rarely adopted any other roles than participant. Citizen collectives (e.g., communities, social movements) were also usually participants, and occasionally also played advisory and expert roles. There is a similar pattern for third sector organisations, such as NGOs, but these groups were quite often involved as organisers and implementers. The role of funder was usually played by elected officials or civil servants working for government agencies. Specialised consultancies were the most common implementers of initiatives. Academics were often involved as experts and to a lesser extent as organisers, advisors, and in some cases as implementers.

Figure 9. Roles of actors across citizen engagement initiatives

Figure 9 shows which groups were responsible for decision-making role on issue(s) of concern, participant selection, methods of engagement, proposed solutions and evaluation criteria. Citizens often took the lead role in the proposed solutions, supported more or less equally by the other actor groups. In some initiatives, citizens also decided on the issues of concern that the process focused on, but few initiatives reported citizen decision-making power in other aspects.

Figure 10. Decision-making roles of actors across citizen engagement initiatives

Engagement methods

There were a wide variety of methods used by the initiatives registered, with on average, 3-4 methods registered per engagement process. ‘Meetings’ was the most- reported method and also the least likely to be accompanied by other methods (11 initiatives reported only ‘meetings’). Workshops were the second-most common method, followed by, webinars and live streams, training sessions, surveys and focus groups.

Figure 11. Methods used for engagement

Type of output and scope

Recommendations (34) were by far the most common output produced, followed by somewhat similar outputs such as decisions on concept or proposals to the elected officials. Other options reported included improved implementation methods, customised local activities, expansion plans; the definition of adaptative pathways and a portfolio of solutions; or design decisions, architectural drawings and materials selection. One initiative developed a climate inventory. Linked to climate data this aimed to collect and disseminate climate adaptation materials.

In all cases, the scope of the output was the geographical scale at which the initiative had been conducted.

Evaluation and impact

Only 25 initiatives out of 61 have data on whether any form of evaluation was carried out. From those that had information about the evaluation process, there is an almost even split between those with (13) and those without (12). However, because these numbers include citizen assemblies which generally include an independent advisory board supervising the engagement process, few other engagement types appear to have been evaluated.

Few entries reported any outcomes, but for those where data is available, they credited the initiative with greater stakeholder engagement, capacity building and the facilitation of knowledge sharing. In one case, the ambitious recommendations generated by citizens reportedly encouraged elected officials to be bolder in their adaptation planning. Other entries mentioned how the initiative had lasting effects; one example of which is captured in the quotes below:

- "At the end of this process of participation, the request emerged, as constantly represented in the various meetings, to create a permanent system of relations organized at various levels and commensurate with the various responsibilities, to be organized by strengthening and structuring the current existing models. [The key] of this system would be to develop an appropriate risk culture, as an essential prerequisite for an effective flood management policy capable of integrating the actions of preparation, protection, forecasting and return to normality." (AdBPo-a, 2016, p. 15).

4.2.1. Key points and summary

The main findings of the analysis of databases and the data analysis on the mapped initiatives are:

- Deliberative forms of citizen engagement are taking place across countries at several governance levels, but climate change adaptation seems to be an issue of concern less present relative to other key issues, such as mitigation.
- Initiatives often address climate change adaptation in general, though some issues are also frequently considered, such as those related to urban planning, energy and/or natural resources related to adaptation strategies.
- Deliberative processes take many forms, but the most visible efforts relate to citizen assemblies (a specific example of mini-publics).
- Initiatives often aim for several goals, including those related to the key values of deliberative democracy.
- The timespan varies greatly across types of initiatives, but it is consistent within types with citizen assemblies on average the longest lasting type of processes.
- Meetings are the most common method, followed by workshops and webinars.
- The most common output was recommendations.
- Few CEIs have an evaluation process.

Finally, it is important to note the role of citizens and other actors in this type of processes. Returning to the interpretation in section 3, where we mentioned how public participation is understood for this mapping exercise to imply substantial engagement with citizens, and in which it "includes a careful examination of a problem or issue, the identification of possible solutions, the establishment or reaffirmation of evaluative criteria, and the use of these criteria in identifying an optimal solution." (cf. Gastil, 2000:20, in Delli Carpini et al., 2004). In many initiatives citizens take

several decision-making roles. Primarily this involves deciding upon recommendations, but in some cases also on the issues of concern or the preferred methods of engagement.

5. Next steps

5.1. Foundation for 1.2

The insights gained through the design and execution of T1.1 provide the basis for T1.2's analysis of citizen engagement methodologies which will involve an expert survey (see the interim report for T1.2 for details on the design), which was in part shaped by efforts carried out in T1.1. While searching for the initiatives in academic and grey literature during the mapping exercise, we also gathered a list of experts to approach for T1.2. We aim to contact different types of actors (from specialised consultancies to academics) that have experience with CEIs, especially seeking to overcome the availability bias for well-resourced initiatives and to include practices and lessons learned from smaller initiatives.

5.2. Life beyond AGORA

Although Task 1.1 officially concludes with the submission of this deliverable, the activities undertaken under its umbrella will continue, especially with regards the mapping efforts for initiatives not registered in other databases. This will be achieved through keeping the registration tool open, making it available in the Digital AGORA and community hub, and continuing to disseminate it during events and networking activities. Moreover, as the CEIs will be displayed online, we hope that more people will feel encouraged to share their experiences. Although the Digital AGORA design is still being finalised, the figure below shows a screenshot of the likely format in which the CEIs will be displayed online.

Finally, in the hope of extending the project legacy further, we have also registered AGORA as a resource in the EC's Community of Practice on Participatory and Deliberative Democracy, which is a research centre building a network of experts, resources and initiatives which are working on citizen engagement in Europe.

Figure 12. Screenshot of the AGORA community hub databases where CEIs will be displayed

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Appendix

Detailed information on two key databases that include CEIs

Name	CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT EU
Website	https://www.citizen-engagement.eu/
Key theme	Compilation of citizen engagement methods with resources and some with real-world examples across the globe
Types of initiatives	All kind
Earliest initiative	2016 (Valencia)
Latest initiative	2019 (Utrecht)
Location	Global
Number of cases	90
Dimensions mapped	Participation level; Target group; Number of participants; Frequency; Duration/Timeline; Implementation; Budget
Fitting cases	None. Not targeting climate change adaptation, outside the EU or < 2018, participation level lesser than collaboration.
Contributors	Frauenhofer Institute (leading) and project partners
Related projects	SPARCS
Mentioned projects	IRIS, MAtchUP, POCITYF
Related academic research	Shortall, R., Mengolini, A., & Gangale, F. (2022). Citizen engagement in EU collective action energy projects. <i>Sustainability</i> , 14(10), 5949.
Description of the database	<p>This rich database was compiled under the H2020-funded project SPARCS (Sustainable energy Positive & zero cARbon CommunitieS, 2019-2024) and hosted by Frauenhofer Institute. It contains a wide range of citizen engagement methods listed with a description of the method, resources and examples across cities in the world. The database distinguishes between three degrees of citizen engagement (inform, consult and collaborate), with 24 resources listed under ‘collaboration’ with citizens as target group. The majority of examples in this subset are in the fields of energy, air quality and urban planning. From the resources listed, 16 contacts were identified.</p>

Name	PARTICIPEDIA
Website	https://participedia.net/
Key theme	Public participation and democratic innovations
Types of initiatives	All kind
Earliest initiative	2013 (Monnheim)
Latest initiative	2024 (Australia)
Location	Global (158 countries represented)
Dimensions mapped	Reviewed by Participedia Editorial Board; Countries; General Issues; Scope of Influence; Purpose/Goal; Approach; Spectrum of Public Participation; Open to All or Limited to Some?; Recruitment Method for Limited Subset of Population; General Types of Methods; Face-to-Face, Online, or Both; Type of Organizer/Manager; Type of Funder; Types of Change; Entry Completeness.
Number of cases	2225
Fitting cases	19 54 ‘maybe’. Exclusion criteria: not targeting climate change adaptation, outside the EU or < 2018, participation level lesser than collaboration.
Contributors	Several institutions; crowd-sourcing
Related projects	Participedia is a networking initiative
Mentioned projects	-
Related academic research	Gastil, J., Richards, R. C., Ryan, M., & Smith, G. (2017). Testing assumptions in deliberative democratic design: A preliminary assessment of the efficacy of the Participedia data archive as an analytic tool. <i>Journal of Public Deliberation</i> , 13(2).

The participedia database is one of the most compelling databases existing related to citizen engagement. The efforts started 2013 from an interinstitutional collaboration led in the US and it is meant as a crowdsourced database. In the mission statement in the website, the description reads as follows (accessed April 2024): “Participedia is a global network and crowdsourcing platform for researchers, educators, practitioners, policymakers, activists, and anyone interested in democratic innovations. (...). Our mission is to mobilize knowledge about democracy-enhancing practices and institutions that people are inventing, remolding, protecting, and transferring from other contexts.”

